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Modelling Wild Boar abundance at high resolution

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Abstract

By using the latest available data, we provide estimates of wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) distribution and abundance pre-African Swine Fever (ASF) based on occurrence data in Europe. Secondly, as a basis for the calibration model output into densities, we used the predictions of relative abundance, and hunting yield-based model (hunted individuals per km²), at 2x2 km for wild boar (by ENETWILD Consortium) and local wild boar densities (individuals per km²) considered reliable and obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as well as some from recent literature (2015 onwards). Hunting yield predictions were considered at different spatial scales namely 5, 10 and 15 km radii buffer around localities with density estimations. The calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities are a better fit for 15 km radius buffer and a significant relationship between model predictions of hunting yield and reliable density values at European level. This calibration of wild boar hunting yield-based model into densities will offer the possibility to predict density values of wild boar. This will be useful to incorporate into risk factor analyses for African Swine Fever at the selected spatial range. This is the first time that absolute density estimates have been made using these two approaches for Europe, which demonstrates the added value of the observatory approach (a number of study areas where reliable density values are obtained, such as from the EOW) to generate novel information of high value for epidemiological assessment. During an ASF outbreak hunting effort will change dramatically and will take a few years to return to similar pre-ASF levels, so post-ASF estimates of density would be limited to areas where ASF has been present for a while. However, there will be relatively limited effect on sighting data as these rely on a number of different actors, many of whom may be expected to return to normal activities relatively soon after ASF arrives. Thus, relative post-ASF wild boar density may be more reliable in the short term. These relative post-ASF densities were calculated but with the limited sighting data available at the chosen locations the uncertainty was high. We advocate for the developing this network of wildlife monitoring across Europe, and in general, harmonized wildlife monitoring programs, ensuring standardisation and consistency in the data generated and collected, which is essential for assessing management and risks related not only to ASF but other wildlife diseases.

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Summary

The spread of diseases such as African Swine Fever (ASF) depends on many factors, including host distribution and population density. To provide two independent estimates for the Europe-wide wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) distribution and abundance we use the latest sighting data collated from GBIF (which is where new *iMammalia* data are stored), along with the latest available hunting data collected by the ENETWILD consortium. The model outputs are supplied at a 2x2 km scale.

The occurrence model method has been updated to account for the clustering of sightings and different sighting effort in parts of Europe. This provides an improved estimate of pre-ASF wild boar abundance. These abundance estimates were then related to the ENETWILD wild boar density estimates from the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as well as some from recent the literature (2015 onwards) to produce density estimates for the chosen areas, Latvia, Lithuania and Italy.

The hunting yield (HY) model method is described in previous reports. Secondly, as a basis for the calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities, we used the model predictions of hunting yields at 2x2 km for wild boar (by ENETWILD Consortium). In total, 77 values of density were used where hunting is practiced and were free of African Swine Fever (at the moment of the study). For each location, the median values of the predicted densities of hunted animals were extracted at buffers of 5, 10 and 15 km of radii, respectively (three spatial resolutions).

The calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities provided a clear relationship between model predictions of HYs and reliable density values at European level. The model fitted for 15 km radio buffer was selected. The calibration of wild boar HY-based model into densities offers the possibility to estimate predicted density values of wild boar (in terms of number of individuals km⁻²). This will be useful to incorporate into risk factor analyses for ASF at the selected spatial range.

These results demonstrate the added value of the observatory approach (an increasing number of study areas where reliable density estimates are obtained by a harmonised methodology) to generate novel information of high value for epidemiological assessment. This is also the first time that absolute density estimates have been made using these approaches for Europe. Further work will refine this approach as more data becomes available.

During an ASF outbreak hunting effort may be halted or supplemented and thus increase the hunting yields. Therefore, the change in effort will result in a change in predicted density, even without accounting for the effect of ASF. Hunting effort will take a few years to return to similar pre-ASF levels, so post-ASF estimates of density, based on hunting yield would likely be limited to areas where ASF has been present for a while. We have therefore not used this approach for the hunting yield data in this report. We advocate for the continuous developing this network of wildlife monitoring across Europe, and in general, harmonized wildlife monitoring programs, ensuring standardisation and consistency in the data generated and collected, which is essential for assessing management and risks related not only to ASF, but other wildlife diseases.

Post-ASF outbreak, there will also likely be less effect on mammal sighting data as these rely on a number of different actors, many of whom may be expected to return to normal activities relatively soon after ASF arrives, although this will depend on public accessibility to ASF-affected areas. Thus, using sighting data to estimate relative post-ASF wild boar density may be more reliable in the short term. For sighting data, the relative proportion of sightings of wild boar compared to other species, before and after the occurrence of ASF should be an

indicator of the relative change in density. These relative post-ASF densities were calculated but with the limited sighting data available at the chosen locations the uncertainty was high. In areas with a greater number of sighting data pre and post-ASF, this approach could be a reliable method to estimate the effect of ASF on wild boar density.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and terms of reference as provided by the requestor

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to: Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO). Contract/Grant title: Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment, contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01.

The work package 4.1A of specific contract 01 of this framework contract was to produce modelled wild boar abundance estimations at the finest resolution for selected locations (locations provided by EFSA: Italy, Latvia and Lithuania) and times (before ASF introduction and a trial post-ASF investigation).

1.2 Scope of the report

The European Commission (EC) needs regular updated epidemiological analysis of the ASF evolution, based on the data collected from the Member States affected by ASFV Genotype II. In addition, updated insights on the risk factors involved in ASF introduction into new territories, disease spread and persistence in Europe are required to be able to update the disease prevention, control, and management policies. EFSA has received the mandate from the EC to provide technical and scientific assistance by reviewing, identifying and describing the risk factors involved in the occurrence, spread and persistence of the ASF virus in the wild boar population, with a view to inform risk management and enable the preparation of future risk assessment mandates. The analyses should consider the knowledge acquired in previous EFSA opinions and scientific reports on ASF. The risk factor analysis should include the identification of new scientific evidence on the risk factors involved in the occurrence, spread and maintenance of ASF virus. Among those risk factors, the EC requested to study in detail the influence of wild boar density on ASF epidemiology. Therefore, the first work to be done is to improve the existing data on wild boar densities. To do so, here we produce estimates for wild boar abundance which are then combined with data to provide estimates of density. First, we updated modelled wild boar suitability estimations based on occurrence data to update estimations of wild boar probability of presence, a relevant parameter to be used in further risk analysis (see next section) together with population density. Secondly, as a basis for the calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities, we used the predictions of hunting yield for wild boar modelled at 2x2 km (by ENETWILD Consortium) and wild boar densities obtained by camera trapping and REM method in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as well as some reliable values extracted from recent literature (2015 onwards).

1.3 Additional information

This report builds on previous predictions of wild boar distribution using hunting data and occurrence data (ENETwild consortium et al. 2018, ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2019a, ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2019b, ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2021, ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022a, ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022b) which are updated and refined.

2 Data and Methodologies

The EFSA working group (WG) on ASF agreed on using the highest spatial resolution available for all models implemented. Thus, the outputs presented here are at 2X2 km grid.

2.1 Occurrence model

2.1.1 Data

Sightings of terrestrial mammal species including wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) were obtained from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) on 08/12/2023 (<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.au5w7a>). Records were filtered to only include presences based on human observation with a coordinate uncertainty less than 2 km from 1986 (year after release of the last European Mammal Atlas; EMMA <https://www.european-mammals.org/>) to 2023. Spatial extent of sightings was restricted to terrestrial land mass within the continent of Europe.

One of the objectives of this work was to provide an estimate of wild boar distribution and abundance prior to the introduction of African swine fever (ASF) in Europe. As such it is necessary to differentiate sightings made pre-ASF from those made post-ASF introduction. Data on ASF outbreaks was obtained from WAHIS/WOAH providing the location and date for all positive reported cases in a wild context. Introductions/outbreaks were defined by the earliest report date on a regional basis using the Database of Global Administrative Boundaries (GADM) level 1 description (https://gadm.org/download_world.html). Any sightings made within these regions after the initial introduction date were identified so that they could be separated from those made prior to ASF introduction (Figure 1).

To model wild boar distribution, both survey effort (biased reporting) and species range (dispersal limitations/stationarity) need to be considered. It is important in all models that presences are contextualised in terms of survey effort. As wild boar are relatively common throughout their range it has been proposed that sightings of other mid to large terrestrial mammals (Figure 2) provide a suitable proxy to measure survey effort (Phillips and Dudík 2008, Croft and Smith 2019, Coomber et al. 2021). On the other hand, there are two main options to describe a long term “stable” species range: (i) use proximity around known presences over time to build up a picture of consistent occurrence; e.g., based on Localised Convex Hulls (Maes et al. 2015); (ii) use expert-derived range maps which provide a broad-scale outline (~100 km accuracy) of long-term occurrence (30 years). For simplicity here we adopt the latter (Figure 3) combining information from expert-derived range maps from both IUCN (IUCN 2021) and Map of life (Wilson et al. 2009-2019, Burgin et al. 2020, Mammal Diversity Database 2020).

As it has been previously done throughout the ENETWILD project (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022b), we consider the same environmental variables describing climate, land cover/use, topography, and anthropogenic influence to explain species presence (Table 1). Environmental variables, particularly those relating to climate, can contain high levels of co-correlation which have the potential to confound models. To mitigate this issue, we performed an initial Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis (Naimi et al. 2014) across the full model extent (Europe) iteratively removing variables until none remained with VIF score above a strict threshold of 2 (minimal co-correlation).

Figure 1: Map showing date of first ASF introduction. Darker colours indicate earlier date of introduction.

Figure 2: Map of wild boar occurrence and survey effort defined by sightings of other "associated" mammal species.

Figure 3: Map showing presence of wild boar (GBIF) in relation to assumed species range for wild boar (combined IUCN & Map of Life).

Table 1: Environmental variables used to model wild boar occurrence.

Code	Variable description	Code	Variable description
BIO1	Annual mean temperature	lc_10	Cropland, rainfed
BIO2	Mean diurnal range (mean monthly max temp - min temp)	lc_11	Herbaceous cover
BIO3	Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) (x100)	lc_12	Tree or shrub cover
BIO4	Temperature seasonality (SDx100)	lc_20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding
BIO5	Max temperature of warmest month	lc_30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)
BIO6	Min temperature of coldest month	lc_40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)
BIO7	Temperature annual range (BIO5-BIO6)	lc_60	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
BIO8	Mean temperature of the Wettest Quarter	lc_61	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)
BIO9	Mean temperature of the Driest Quarter	lc_70	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
BIO10	Mean temperature of warmest quarter	lc_71	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)
BIO11	Mean temperature of coldest quarter	lc_80	Tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
BIO12	Annual precipitation	lc_90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)
BIO13	Precipitation of wettest month	lc_100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)
BIO14	Precipitation of driest month	lc_110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)
BIO15	Precipitation seasonality (coefficient of variation)	lc_120	Shrubland
BIO16	Precipitation of wettest quarter	lc_122	Deciduous shrubland
BIO17	Precipitation of driest quarter	lc_130	Grassland
BIO18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	lc_140	Lichens and mosses
BIO19	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	lc_150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)
GROW	Length of vegetation growing period	lc_152	Sparse shrub (<15%)
SUNRAD	Sun radiation	lc_153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)
SNOW	Snow cover	lc_160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water
HFP	Human Footprint Index	lc_180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water
ALT	Mean altitude	lc_190	Urban areas
		lc_200	Bare areas
		lc_201	Consolidated bare areas
		lc_202	Unconsolidated bare areas
		lc_210	Water bodies
		lc_220	Permanent snow and ice

2.1.2 Model methodology

Throughout the ENETWILD project we have considered a range of approaches to model distribution requiring increasing levels of assumption/processing of the available occurrence data. Here, we consider presence-background modelling using Maxent (Phillips et al. 2004). Presence-background models such as Maxent (Phillips et al. 2004) allow consideration for incorporating biased survey effort comparing environmental samples from presence locations against those from surveyed locations (both where wild boar have been detected and where they have not) to infer presence. Assuming non-detection locations represent true absence, predictions can be assumed to reflect probability of presence rather than just an index of relative suitability. Initial predictions were made using all occurrence data, excluding any records post-ASF introduction and sites beyond the assumed stable species range, and a subset of environmental variables, further excluding any that were significantly co-correlated across training locations. These predictions indicated some clear bias towards surveyed regions. This is likely because of clustering/oversampling leads to spatial autocorrelation in occurrence of wild boar (locations close to wild boar populations are more likely to report presence even though they are not suitable). To account for this issue, we consider spatial thinning of surveyed data, subsampling locations at random to maintain a minimum spacing (Aiello-Lammens et al. 2015). The degree (optimal distance) of thinning can be difficult to determine. There have been several approaches proposed examining spatial autocorrelation in both occurrence data and environmental variables. Here, we adopted an approach of trial and error, systematically increasing thinning distance until training AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve) statistic which measures the degree to which variables explain data) first peaked (Figure 4). This exercise suggested a minimum thinning distance of approximately 60 km which is similar to reported maximum dispersal distances for the species (Santini et al. 2013). For simplicity, rather than performing stochastic Monte Carlo based thinning we apply a deterministic approach (Smith et al. 2023)(geoThin), to fit a single model and generate a suitability prediction.

Figure 4: Plot showing model performance measured using training AUC based on subsampling of data locations to ensure an increasing minimum spacing. Optimal minimum spacing appears to occur around 60 km which matches the dispersal distance for wild boar.

2.1.3 Estimating density based on habitat suitability

Using outputs of the species distribution modelling, in conjunction with reliable density estimates provided by the European Observatory of Wildlife (see Table 2), a Pan-European density map for Wild Boar was generated. For each study site, in which a density estimate was provided, calculated based on Random Encounter Modelling (REM), a corresponding boundary polygon was generated; to which said estimate was assigned. The resultant shapefile layer was rasterised to a resolution of 1 x 1km (1km²) and used to extract the underlying habitat suitability value from the SDM output. Those cells, for which a corresponding density and suitability value were extracted, were then used for density modelling.

Density modelling was performed using a generalised linear model (GLM), with density provided as a response variable, and suitability provided as a predictor (i.e. density ~ suitability). The GLM was fitted with a gamma distribution due to right-skewed, non-normal response data (i.e. density), even following appropriate transformation. Once fitted, the model was used to predict wild boar densities across Europe, using the entire SDM dataset as a predictor. The resulting map, showing predicted wild boar density throughout Europe was further modified so that for those cells in which suitability fell below a specific threshold (0.34), density was estimated at 0 individuals/km², due to an expected absence of wild boar in these regions. In addition, this density map was subsequently clipped using country-level geographic boundaries (i.e. NUTS 0), to focus on three specific regions; Italy, Latvia, and Lithuania as defined by EFSA.

2.1.4 Estimating relative post-ASF density based on occurrence data

Using the occurrence data extracted from GBIF we compute the recording rate (proportion of total mammal sightings reporting wild boar) by region (GADM levels) and by year from 2008 (a year before the first recorded introduction of ASF in Europe) to 2023. To account for inconsistent survey effort we exclude any regions where boar is not consistently reported (at least one boar reported per year) across all 16 years of the time period. For each region, we produce a trend in recording rate relative to the 2008 value by comparing aggregated trends between ASF-unaffected (baseline wild boar population trend) and ASF-affected regions we suggest it may be possible to infer some insight into the relative impact of ASF on wild boar density.

2.2 Hunting-yield model

2.2.1 Data

As a basis for the calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities, we used the predictions of hunting yields from the 2x2 model for wild boar by ENETWILD Consortium 2022b) (see Figure 5).

Wild boar densities obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW) based on camera trapping, as well as some from recent the literature (2015 onwards, see Figure 6 and Table 2 including reliable densities as recommended by ENETWILD consortium et al. 2021). Concretely, 77 values of density were used where hunting is practiced and free

of African Swine Fever. For each location, the median values of the predicted densities of hunted animals were extracted at buffers of 5, 10 and 15 km radii respectively (three spatial resolutions).

Figure 5. Predictions of hunting yields as the 2x2 model for wild boar by ENETWILD Consortium 2022b) (<https://zenodo.org/records/10809293>).

Figure 6. Locations (yellow dots) where wild boar densities were obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW) over the predictions of hunting yields at 2x2 km, as well as some from recent the literature.

Table 2: Wild boar densities obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as well as some from recent the literature (2015 onwards).

Country	Name study site	ASF presence	Administrative figure	Bioregion	Area (ha)	LON	LAT	Year	Density (ind/km ²)	SE density	CV density	Method density
Bulgaria	Voden-Iri Hisar	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	8000	26.683	43.665	2022	4.38	1.84	42	REM
Croatia	Senj	0	Hunting ground	Southern	3548	14.916178	45.01248	2022	4.09	2.11		REM
Czech Rep.	The Bohemian Switzerland National Park	0	Protected Area	Eastern	8000	14.381	50.876	2022	1.24		28.8	REM
Italy	La Mandria	0	Protected Area	Western	1604	7.57	45.158	2022	15.26	2.41	15.79	REM
Italy	CACN1/Val Maira	0	Hunting ground	Western	34851	8.538	45.665	2022	10.09	3.37	33.39	REM
Italy	Alpe di Catenaiia	0	Protected Area	Western	2700	11.9123	43.667367	2022	25.83	6.97	27	REM
Poland	Białowieża Forest	1	Hunting ground	Eastern	2947	23.75650	52.75659	2022	0.42	0.26	61	REM
Portugal	ZCA Santulhão	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2948	-6.641	41.573	2022	1.8	1.08	59.82	REM
Portugal	Castreja	0	Hunting ground	Western	2470	-8.136	42.042	2022	6.39	2.65	41.44	REM
Portugal	Lombada	0	Hunting ground	Southern	21184	-6.606	41.864	2022	2.79	1.12	40.12	REM
Portugal	Murça	0	Hunting ground	Western	6404	-7.434	41.461	2022	2.07	0.77	37.13	REM
Portugal	Castelo Melhor	0	Hunting ground	Southern	3329	-7.081	41.04	2022	1.95	0.74	38.14	REM
Portugal	Cubeira	0	Hunting ground	Southern	1812	-7.219	39.677	2022	6.75	1.46	21.67	REM
Portugal	Arrábida	0	Protected Area	Southern	36283	-9.029	38.518	2022	18.45	6.36	34.46	REM
Portugal	Bicas da Serra	0	Hunting ground	Southern	1129	-7.932	37.199	2022	16.26	6.45	39.65	REM
Portugal	Tolosa	0	Hunting ground	Southern	4695	-7.735	39.41	2022	2.92	0.86	29.55	REM
Spain	Parque Natural Sierra del Carche	0	Protected Area	Southern	5942	-1.164	38.427	2022	0.85	0.26		REM
Spain	Riofrio	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2500	-4.105	39.105	2022	4.88	1.9	38.93	REM
Spain	Donana	0	Protected Area	Southern	7000	-6.464	36.959	2022	2.9	2.2	0.38	REM

Spain	Arriola (Araba)	0	Hunting ground	Western	4000	- 2.389 222	42.94 0055	20 22	4.27	0.76	17.8 2	REM
Spain	Montgó (Alacant)	0	Protected Area	Southern	2086	0.172 210	38.80 1133	20 22	14.47	9.59	66.2 8	REM
Spain	Cabanes-Torreblanca (Castellón)	0	Protected Area	Southern	850	0.188 4	40.17 56	20 22	41.55	16.1 3	38.8 1	REM
Spain	Serra Calderona Natural Park - Porta Coeli (Spain)	0	Protected Area	Southern	2918	- 0.322 553	38.96 4662	20 22	14.49	5.57	39.0 6	REM
Turkey	Kartdag Wildlife Reserve	0	Protected Area	Southern	11495	33.34 1	41.78 2	20 22	2.45	1.55	63.3 1	REM
Andorra	Vedat de caça de la Vall de Ransol	0	Protected Area	Western	2813	1.644 1	42.60 36	20 22	0.193	0.14	70.1 7	REM
Belgium	Marche-en-Famenne	0	Protected Area	Western	2500	5.365 034	50.25 2736	20 22	30.99	10.0 7	32.5	REM
Belgium	Game Management Ulnit 7	0	Hunting ground	Western	10000	4.694	50.80 2	20 22	8.6	2.93	34.0 6	REM
Bosnia&Herzegovina	Romanija	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	6000	18.48 68	43.56 27	20 22	2.23	1.6	73.0 7	REM
France	Marais Noir de Saint-Coulban	0	Protected Area	Western	1500	- 1.911 492	48.56 65	20 22	2.61	1.3	49.6 3	REM
Georgia	Lagodekhi National Park	0	Protected Area	Eastern	24450	46.31 5	41.87 6926	20 22	0.57	0.32	56	REM
Hungary	Gemenc	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	20000	18.87 3	46.21 7	20 22	8.07	5.72	71.5	REM
Israel	Ramat Hanadiv Nature park	0	Protected Area	Southern	1160	34.92 6	32.55 4	20 22	20.88	9.1	44	REM
Lithuania	MMMPV	1	Protected Area	Eastern	5646	21.91 205	56.02 331	20 22	0.52	1.42	35.1 6	REM
Montenegro	Orjen Mountain	0	Hunting ground	Southern	6000	18.55 1724	42.62	20 22	2.85	1.68	58.8 2	REM
Netherlands	Veluwe	0	Hunting ground	Western	2000	5.7	52.23	20 22	2.05	1.02	50	REM
Romania	Covasna	1	Hunting ground	Eastern	6000	25.92 5195	45.92 6571	20 22	0.62	0.43		REM
Serbia	Studnica	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	11000	20.26 31	43.33 20	20 22	2.2	1.05	47.7 8	REM

Slovakia	Javorie	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	10000	19.140291	48.534234	2022	4.73	2.18	46	REM
Slovenia	Vrhe Vrabče	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	3950	13.943659	45.777460	2022	7.131	2.49	35	REM
Slovenia	Rižana (Primorsko HMD)	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	3657	13.8540	45.5380	2022	11.12	4.34	39.08	REM
Sweden	Stalbo	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2500	17.12471	60.01757	2022	2.81	3.23	114.79	REM
Poland	Gora Kalwaria	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	4655	21.428	51.865	2021	7.66	4.63	60.444	REM
Belarus	Naliboki Forest	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	14100	26.597	53.981	2021	7.41	1.84	24.831	REM
Germany	Alt Oerrel	0	Hunting ground	Western	4130	10.201	52.961	2021	3.38	1.19	35.207	REM
Germany	Süsing	0	Hunting ground	Western	2720	10.334	53.089	2021	2.31	0.87	37.662	REM
Czech Rep.	Niva	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2000	16.851	49.445	2021	17.09	7.42	43.417	REM
Bulgaria	Voden-Iri Hisar	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	8000	26.683	43.665	2021	2.35	0.86	36.596	REM
Bulgaria	Panagyurishte	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2000	24.42	42.494	2021	2.51	1.67	66.534	REM
Croatia	Biokovo	0	Hunting ground	Southern	20000	17.052	43.328	2021	0.35	0.24	68.571	REM
Croatia	Prolom	0	Hunting ground	Southern	7700	16.099	45.253	2021	6.54	1.14	17.431	REM
North Macedonia	Mrezicko	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2500	22.095	41.163	2021	37.23	10.74	28.848	REM
Albania	Çajupi Mountain (Gjirokastra region)	0	Protected Area	Southern	24447	20.146	42.046	2021	1.5	0.49	32.667	REM
Turkey	Kartdag Wildlife Reserve	0	Protected Area	Southern	11495	33.341	41.782	2021	5.75	2.4	41.739	REM
Italy	La Mandria	0	Protected Area	Western	1604	7.57	45.158	2021	15.25	2.41	15.803	REM
Italy	15. CACN3	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	73000	8.393	45.665	2021	5.84	2.12	36.301	REM
Spain	Amurrio (Araba)	0	Hunting ground	Western	6000	-2.961	43.049	2021	2.12	0.83	39.151	REM
Spain	Riglos (Huesca)	0	Hunting ground	Western	2500	-0.643	42.365	2021	11.31	4.11	36.34	REM
Spain	Parque Natural Sierra del Carche	0	Protected Area	Southern	2100	-1.151	38.427	2021	4.08	1.63	39.951	REM

Portugal	ZCA Santulhão	0	Hunting ground	South ern	2948	-6.641	41.573	2021	3.071	0.794	25.855	REM
Spain	Navarra Eslava	0	Hunting ground	South ern	3500	-1.493	42.595	2018	2.37	3.55		REM
Spain	Parc natural Serra de Mariola (ZCC Agres)	0	Hunting ground	South ern	2450	-0.499	38.76	2018	5.71	3.12		REM
Spain	Valencia Ciutretonda	0	Hunting ground	South ern	4400	-0.376	38.987	2018	13.99	19.8		REM
Spain	Avila Becedas	0	Hunting ground	South ern	2700	-5.651	40.48	2018	3.24	1.7		REM
Spain	Catalunya Montseny	0	Hunting ground	South ern	1500	2.333	41.744	2018	9.5	8.31		REM
Spain	Asturias Sueve	0	Hunting ground	South ern	1800	-5.229	42.452	2018	5.24	2.19		REM
Spain	Quintos Mora	0	Hunting ground	South ern	6600	-4.111	39.368	2018	8.56	7.21		REM
Spain	Parc natural de la Serra d'Irta	0	Protecte d Area	South ern	2690	0.317	40.33	2022	4.33	3.21	74.22	REM
Spain	Parc natural del Desert de les Palmes	0	Protecte d Area	South ern	3096	0.038	40.089	2022	74.29	33.14	44.61	REM
Spain	Parc natural Serra de Mariola (ZCC Agres)	0	Protecte d Area	South ern	715	-0.499	38.76	2022	4.87	2.8	58.24	REM
Spain	Parc natural Font Roja (Refugi Fau)	0	Protecte d Area	South ern	525	-0.54	38.656	2022	5.9	3.07	52.11	REM
Poland	Czarna Bialostocka Forest District	1	Hunting ground	Easte rn	6890	23.508	53.199	2021-2022	0.18			UAV thermal
Portugal	Castro Laboreiro and Lamas de Mouro	0	Protecte d Area	West ern	3000	-8.18	41.5	2015-2021	2.59		22	DS-CT
Italy	Casentino	0	Hunting ground	West ern	15400	11.49	43.48	2013-2020	14			CMR
Italy	Alpe della Luna	0	Protecte d Area	West ern	1540	12.166	43.651	2019	3.5	2		Faec al counts
Italy	Berignone	0	Protecte d Area	West ern	2200	10.95	43.331	2019	12.5	3.6		Faec al

3 Results

3.1 Modelled occurrence of wild boar

A single model output of suitability prediction was produced (Figure 7). We evaluated our model by exploring the importance of different variables and comparing this with the known characteristics of the species; key land cover variables describing conditions such as shelter (trees and shrubs) and resources (crops and grassland) and climatic variables relating to drought (Table 3). We also assessed the transferability of our model by performing a MESS analysis (Figure 8) which highlighted minimal regions where environmental conditions are not represented by the model training data suggesting predictions were reliable. The training AUC of the final model was 0.89.

To assess the impact of ASF on wild boar abundance we propose comparing the reporting rate of the species against other associated species. We conjecture that any reductions observed beyond the standard inter-annual variation reflects a change (in this case decrease) in population numbers and therefore this data could be used as a proxy to measure relative changes in density due to ASF.

Table 3: Maxent variable importance

Variable	Percent contribution	Permutation importance
GROW	16.3	13
BIO18	9.6	12
lc_60	8.9	7.3
lc_11	7.4	4.6
lc_10	6.4	7.9
ALT	5.5	5.8
lc_120	4.8	2.7
HFP	4.5	7.5
lc_210	3.8	2.8
lc_40	3.4	3.6
lc_150	3.3	3.6
lc_90	2.9	3.1
GPW	2.7	5
lc_30	2.7	3.5
lc_200	2.5	3
lc_20	2.5	1.8
lc_100	2.4	3.8
lc_12	2.3	0.8
BIO19	2.3	2.1
lc_130	2.3	3.6
WIND	1.8	0.6
BIO15	1.5	0.8
lc_180	0.3	0.9

Figure 7: Map showing predicted suitability (probability of presence) for wild boar. Darker colours denote higher probability.

Figure 8: Map showing the coverage of training data in terms of environmental conditions. Training data is broadly representative of all conditions across Europe suggesting predictions can be assumed reliable.

3.1.1 Estimating density based on habitat suitability

When incorporating estimates of both density and suitability into the gamma GLM, the model predicted similar densities across Italy (Figure 9A), Latvia (Figure 9B) and Lithuania (Figure 9C).

Figure 9 A-C. Map showing the predicted pre-ASF density of wild boar, at 2 x 2km resolution, in A) Italy, B) Latvia, and C) Lithuania. Predicted densities are based on reliable density estimates, generated using random encounter modelling, and habitat suitability, generated using species distribution modelling.

3.1.2 Post-ASF estimation

Figure 10 shows changes in the relative recording rate for wild boar which we suggest could be used as a proxy for population trend. The median trend from ASF-unaffected regions suggests boar populations have been reasonably stable since 2008 although the inter-annual variability is high likely due to inconsistencies in survey effort. The median trend for ASF-affected regions shows a notable decline in recording rate in later years following an increased frequency of outbreaks. Synchronising trends to produce changes in recording following an outbreak shows a consistent decline in sightings of wild boar with a reduction of between around 50% and 80% after 3 years. However, it must be noted this is based on data from a limited sample (4 regions). Expanding the analysis to consider GADM level 0 regions allowed inclusion of a further trend which produced a similar pattern in recording for the first 4 years post-ASF introduction and in year 5 showed an increase in the reporting of wild boar which could indicate some recovery. While these results are promising and certainly show that

there is some potential to use occurrence data to infer changes in density further refinement is needed to account for changes to survey protocols and limited/inconsistent sampling.

Figure 10: Plots showing population trends based on changes in recording rate of wild boar from 2008 to 2023 aggregated across GADM level 1 regions (a) unaffected by ASF and (b) affected by ASF. Plots (c) and (d) show relative change in recording wild boar synchronised for each region (four samples based on GADM level 1 in regions where ASF has been present for 3 years and five samples, four plus one additional sample from a region where ASF has been present for 8 years, based on GADM level 0 respectively) against year since initial detection of ASF, standardised by pre-outbreak recording rates. Red line denotes a baseline of zero change. Solid line indicates the median trend and dashed lines denote the 5th and 95th percentiles. Markers in (b) indicate years of new ASF outbreaks.

3.2 Calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities

A summary of the general linear mixed models parameterized for each spatial resolution using the reliable densities values from EOW (log transformed) as response variable, and surface of the sampling location (in hectares and log transformed) and HYs log transformed as fixed factors and the bioregion as random effect factor are shown in Table 4 (see Table 2 for wild boar densities obtained in the framework of the EOW).

Table 4. Summary of the general lineal mixed models parameterized for each spatial resolution using the reliable densities values from EOW (log transformed) as response variable, and surface of the sampling location (in hectares and log transformed) and HYS log transformed as fixed factors and the bioregion as random effect factor). R² marginal (effects only of fixed factors) and R² conditional (effects of both fixed and random factors) were also reported.

Spatial resolution	AIC	R ² m	R ² c
5km	162	0.32	0.37
10km	161	0.32	0.37
15km	159	0.35	0.40

The model fitted for 15 km radius buffer was selected. The statistical parameters of the model are summarized in Table 5 and Figure 11.

Table 5. The statistical parameters of the model.

	Estimate	t-value	p-value
Intercept	5.01	4.153	***
log(surface)	-0.47	-3.406	**
log(HYS)	0.59	3.068	**

Figure 11: Representation of the statistical relationships of the selected model (fitted for 15km radius).

The modelled wild boar density estimation is provided as a geopackage (<https://zenodo.org/records/10809293>) and was obtained by fitting the surface of the study area to the median value in the dataset (3602 ha). Figure 12 displays the calibrated wild boar density values (predictions) at 2x2 km resolution.

a)

b)

Figure 12: Map showing the predicted pre-ASF wild boar density (2x2 km resolution) after the calibration of predicted hunting yields-based abundance on a set of reliable density values for (a) Euopre as a whole and (b) for Italy (A), Latvia (B) and Lithuania (C).

4 Discussion

Two alternative approaches were investigated and/or have been previously used to estimate wild boar distribution and abundance. There are some substantial differences between these outputs, so further work would be required to either determine which is 'more correct' or to combine the methods to provide one more reliable map. In particular, both outputs are extrapolations, and are thus not reliable for areas where wild boar have failed to colonise, such as the islands of Ireland and Great Britain. However, both output agree that higher densities occur in parts of Italy compared to the Baltic.

The calibration of occurrence and hunting yield models into densities shows a clear relationship between model predictions of HYs and density values at the European level. This permits predictions of absolute wild boar density. There is a strong visual similarity between the methods for areas of high or low density within each of the target countries (e.g. western Italy), although the absolute density estimates do vary between methods and no formal comparison has been performed.

Any analysis of risk factors relating wild boar density to occurrence, persistence or spread of ASF could use either the probability of occurrence, the predicted hunting yield or the absolute density estimates from either method.

The effect of ASF on wild boar density using mammal sighting data has been attempted, and the output clearly shows a substantial decrease in density, but with a large uncertainty. This lack of certainty is due to the limited sighting data available in the selected areas both pre and post ASF. In areas of Europe where sighting data are more frequent it would be expected to see a reduction in this uncertainty.

5 Conclusions

- Hunting yield data and sighting data were used to create estimated distribution and abundance of wild boar across Europe.
- The independent occurrence and hunting-yield outputs do not visually have a high level of agreement, and further work is required to ascertain the relative accuracy of each, or to find a method to combine the best of both approaches.
- The calibration of wild boar occurrence and hunting yield model output with density estimate from the European Observatory for Wildlife (EOW)² offers the possibility to predict density values of wild boar (number of individuals km⁻²) across Europe. This is the first time that absolute density estimates have been made using such approaches for Europe.

² <https://wildlifeobservatory.org/>

- This will be useful to incorporate wild boar density into risk factor analyses for African Swine Fever at the selected spatial scale. Overall, we advocate for the continuous developing an such integrated network of wildlife monitoring across Europe, and in general, harmonized wildlife monitoring programs, ensuring standardisation and consistency in the data generated and collected, which is essential for assessing risks and management not only related to ASF, but other wildlife diseases.
- This demonstrates the added value of the observatory approach (a number of study areas where reliable density values are obtained) to generate novel information of high value for epidemiological assessment.

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